

ISic3491

I.Sicily inscription 3491

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Sicilia

Place of origin (modern)

Sicily

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8719

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Κλώδ[ιος]

2. Κλωδ[ίου]

3. χρησ[τός]

4. χ[αῖρε]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645112

EDR 140746

EDCS 41300108

PHI 175749

Bibliography

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika* 6. Palermo. At 144

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